

Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027

D7.4 Project website - concept and initial content

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable describes the concept and initial content of the project website.

1. INTRODUCTION

The ACT4CAP27 website was constructed utilizing the visual identity. The site is organized by PLAB, under the domain www.act4cap27.eu.

The website is intended to be dynamic. The News and Events sections and the rest of the content will be updated at least once a month and managed by the Dissemination Task Leader (PLAB) throughout the lifetime of the project, based upon the inputs from partners, project evolution and evaluation. The information published at the website will be presented in a way that is accessible and understandable by wide range of stakeholders.

Google Analytics has been deployed at this early stage of the project as a tool for reporting key performance indicators (e.g. users, countries of origin, languages, browsers, devices, etc.). The website was designed for use on different types of devices such as desktop, mobile or tablet.

1.1. Website description

An initial version of the ACT4CAP27 project website has been designed, provisioned and deployed on the Internet. It has been designed to address the key questions that external visitors to the website are expected to have:

- What is the project about?
- What is the project progress?
- Who is participating in the project?
- What additional details are available?
- Who to contact for more information?
- How can readers get engaged?

The website will provide information to public audiences. The principal sections of the website are:

- general information about the project,
- partners' details,
- project news,
- list of events,
- all public documents generated during the project,
- links to social network profiles,
- newsletter subscription,
- contact information,
- acknowledgement of EU funding,
- disclaimer.

The sections and the uses for which they are designed are described below.

1.1. The “Home” page

The Home page of the ACT4CAP27 website contains basic information about project. The upper bar on the start screen shows the ACT4CAP27 logo, the brief mission statement “Evidence-based knowledge for agri-food policies” and the main menu bar including links to Home, About, News Events, Capacity building, Resources, Newsletters and the search function.

Below the project full title there are two buttons leading to the About and News pages.

The rest of the page contains highlights of the following pages:

- About
- Events
- News

The section below displays the project partner logos, followed by

- contact information of the project coordinator,
- links to Twitter, YouTube, LinkedIn, ACT4CAP27 Zenodo Community page, and the ACT4CAP27 OpenAIRE page,
- a call to action for subscribing to the project newsletters (handled in MailerLite),
- links to the Privacy and Cookie Policy and Imprint pages.

The footer section contains the acknowledgement to the EC grant (with link to the CORDIS sheet of the project) and disclaimer text.

1.2. The “About” the project page

The page “About the project” presents the overall concept, objectives of the project.

It includes 4 subsections:

- Why ACT4CAP27? – introduction, project objectives, intended impacts
- Work packages – short description of WP objectives, time schedule overview
- Partners – short description of the consortium followed by individual tiles for each partner organisation leading to partner page presenting partner teams.
- Scientific and Policy Advisory Board (SPAB) – short introduction of the internationally recognised professionals and stakeholders with outstanding expertise relevant for ACT4CAP27, advises the project on the central scientific scope and direction of ACT4CAP27, and on research design issues, taking account of new policy and scientific developments and insights.

1.3. The “News” page

This page presents a list of news items with the most recent at the top. It includes items about meetings of the project partners and important pieces of news about the project implementation and short reports about events in which members of the consortium partners are participants, such as conferences, workshops, etc. A teaser of the latest 3 items is also shown in the start page highlights section.

1.4. The “Events” page

This page presents events that are relevant for the topic of the project, starting with upcoming events followed by past events.

1.5. The “Capacity building” page

This page will contain texts on capacity building activities in the project.

A set of capacity building activities will be organized to train newcomers into model-based research and to involve policymakers and end users in policy assessments.

1.6. The “Resources” page

The “Resources” page will contain all material that will be published and will be thus publicly available. Subsections will be added by the website’s content manager PLAB, based upon the project’s requirements.

Planned subsections:

- Public deliverables
- Open-access scientific materials
- Policy briefs
- ACT4CAP27 in public repositories (e.g. OpenAIRE page, Zenodo Community)
- Presentations and posters
- Other publications, including promo material such as the on-line project flyer describing the project aims, objectives and intended outcomes
- Newsletters
- Videos
- Media coverage
- Final conference presentations and videos
- Useful links to external pages that are relevant to ACT4CAP27, including modelling tools, relevant projects, and a related initiative

1.7. The Newsletters page

This page contains a form enabling users for subscribing to the project’s 6 monthly newsletters (handled in MailerLite), and below also displays the available newsletters issued.

1.8. The “Privacy and cookie policy” page

This page describes the GDPR compatible privacy policy and use of cookies related to the ACT4CAP27 website.

1.9. The “Imprint” page

This page describes the terms of use of the ACT4CAP27 website.

2. FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

Short term developments of the website are expected to include:

- monitoring website statistics (new visitors, return visitors, countries of origin, etc.)
- update of website content based on project progress monthly (and on demand when it is needed), mostly in the sections “News”, “Events”.

Longer-term development of the website will include adding short videos introducing the project and its progress.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The ACT4CAP27 website is a key element of the project's communication and results dissemination strategy. The website will ensure the visibility of the project, facilitate the diffusion of the project's results and promote their exploitation.

To orientate the reader and to enable correct referencing in search engines, pages will be tagged with several types of metadata, including the page title, author's name, language, date of creation, description and a number of keywords.

To generate traffic to the website it will be publicised widely including on printed materials, press releases, paper and electronic correspondence, home pages of the project's partners and other relevant websites etc. The ACT4CAP27 website will be registered with appropriate portals to fully exploit the internet's search engine technology. The website traffic will be continuously monitored and reported 6 monthly.

An initial version of the ACT4CAP27 website has been designed, populated with materials, and published on the Internet.

In its initial version, the website consists mostly of static content. It has been designed to ensure that there is a presence of the project on the internet that can answer key questions of external visitors. The project website will evolve as the project grows. The consortium will ensure that the website will exist for at least 5 years after the project funding has finished and that bookmarks and published URLs will continue to function.

4. INITIAL WEBSITE CONTENT – TECHNICAL DESCRIPTION

The "About" the project page

Contains three submenu sections:

- Why ACT4CAP27?
- Work packages
- Partners

Contents of the submenus are as follows:

Submenu 2: HOME > ABOUT > WHY ACT4CAP27?

Welcome to ACT4CAP27

ACT4CAP27 is a European research project aiming to enhance analytical capabilities, tools, and collaborative technical infrastructure within the policy modelling community, to provide support for evidence-based EU agri-food policies post-2027.

WHY ACT4CAP27?

ACT4CAP27 addresses the Work Programme Topic HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-2 - Advancing analytical capacity and tools to support EU agri-food policies post 2027.

The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) stands as the European Union's cornerstone for supporting agriculture, ensuring food security, and driving rural development. Aligned with the objectives of the European Green Deal, encompassing the Farm to Fork and Biodiversity Strategy, the CAP plays a pivotal role in reshaping Europe's agri-food systems for sustainability.

In the evolving landscape of the European Green Deal, existing quantitative modelling tools face a monumental challenge in comprehensively addressing all components of the policy. The need to align with the ambitious goals of the Green Deal, including sustainability and biodiversity, demands a significant enhancement in thematic coverage.

PROJECT OBJECTIVES

The project adopts a comprehensive food system approach, focusing on building analytical capacity for the quantitative assessment of the impacts of upcoming agri-food policies on the economic, social (including health), environmental, and climate sustainability of food systems. It builds on established modelling tools that are used to predict the impacts of climate, agricultural, and forestry policies, at the local, national, and regional levels.

Through the identification of synergies, trade-offs, and linkages, the project enhances the effectiveness and efficiency of regulatory pathways, particularly in the context of ongoing shocks and disruptions across Europe and globally.

Specific objectives

- DESIGNING a conceptual data and modelling framework to operationalize and better understand the determinants and indicators for an improved EU food system performance and ASSESSING policy impact.
- Developing an enhanced modular MODELLING Toolbox to quantify the transition to a sustainable EU food system and its contribution to societal goals.
- SAFEGUARDING the uptake and update of the integrated and modular toolbox and community building.
- PLATFORM for stakeholder interaction and dialogues – at different stages of the project

INTENDED OUTCOMES

Enhancing Analytical Capacity

ACT4CAP27 focuses on enhancing the analytical capacity of key policy tools, including CAPRI, GLOBIOM, MAGNET, and AGMEMOD, utilized by the European Commission.

A Comprehensive Methodological Framework

ACT4CAP27 introduces a consistent, interdisciplinary methodological framework. This framework operationalizes and quantifies relevant aspects of the EU agri-food system and related policies post-2027.

The emphasis is on economic, social (including health), environmental, and climate sustainability impacts, ensuring a holistic understanding of the policy landscape.

ACT4CAP27 Modular Toolbox

Addressing the shortcomings of current policy modelling tools, ACT4CAP27 introduces the Act4CAP27 Modular Toolbox for EU Food System Modelling. This innovative approach creates a collaborative space and modular model infrastructure for the entire EU agri-food research community and beyond. The toolbox serves as a basis for innovation, fostering collective efforts towards sustainable outcomes.

Dissemination & Stakeholder Engagement

The ACT4CAP27 Dissemination and Stakeholder Platform plays a crucial role in establishing an inclusive engagement with stakeholders. This platform seeks to co-create, communicate, and disseminate research results, ensuring that the broader community is actively involved in the transformation process.

Interactive Roadmap for Policy Guidance

ACT4CAP27 goes beyond modelling and tools; it launches an Interactive Roadmap designed to guide EU, national, and regional policymakers. This tool facilitates informed decision-making by helping policymakers weigh up policy objectives towards more sustainable outcomes.

EXPECTED RESULTS

- Novel food systems framework, holistic indicators & gap analysis to guide development of agri-food models.
- Modular Toolbox for Sustainable Food System Policy Modelling to support agricultural modelling capacity of EU member states.
- Assessment of potential future agri-food policy options.
- Monitoring and projecting environmental, social & economic indicators of the EU food system.
- New generation of agri-food system modellers & EU wide community of model practitioners.
- Dissemination & Stakeholder Platform bringing together food system experts and EU modellers and analysts providing them with an open access to the ACT4CAP27 Portal.
- Impact of agricultural policy analysis on performance of the EU food system fostered through a programme of engagement with key stakeholders at regional, country and EU levels.
- ACT4CAP27 Interactive Roadmap with transition narratives and pathways to achieve medium- to long-term sustainable food systems in the EU.

Submenu 2: HOME > ABOUT > Work Packages

WORK PACKAGES

The ACT4CAP27 project is managed through 9 work packages (WP), each of which oversees and/or are responsible for various parts of the five-year project. This is illustrated in the chart below. To view project outputs and deliverables, please go to Resources.

{Project chart goes here}

For more information about each work package click on the following tiles:

WP1 Conceptual framework and analytical tools gap analysis

{tile content}

WP leader: WR

Main objective: Defining an overall conceptual framework of EU food systems for the identification of drivers, indicators and gaps in existing modelling tools to assess policy impacts

Specific objectives:

O1.1 To obtain a framework of EU food systems for analysing determinants of sustainable food system outcomes

O1.2 To identify operational and valid sustainability indicators for policy impact analyses

O1.3 To identify gaps in existing modelling tools for food system-wide agri-food policy impact assessment and identify CAP post 2027 policies

WP2 Coverage of economic, social, environmental and climate sustainability of food systems

{tile content}

WP leader: LSHTM

Main objective: To develop a toolbox of health, environmental, social, and economic assessments modules that will be connected to the extended versions of the existing iMAP models in this project (AGMEMOD, CAPRI, GLOBIOM, MAGNET) and that can be used for stand-alone applications with associated databases to be developed.

Specific objectives:

O2.1 To develop a health module.

O2.2 To develop an environmental impact assessment modules

O2.3 To develop a socio-economic impact assessment module

WP3 Model structures for representation of agro-food systems and policies

{tile content}

WP leader: SLU

Main objective: To extend the capacity of models to analyse critical urgent societal problems (CUSP) relating to agriculture, environment and food systems, in particular in the light of developments identified in WP1, using infrastructure developed in WP4.

Specific objectives:

O3.1 To advance the capacity to model the use of inputs linked to external effects.

O3.2 To advance the capacity to model preference shifts in consumption.

O3.3 To advance the capacity to model changes in the supply chains.

O3.4 To advance the capacity to model changes in policies.

WP4 ACT4CAP27 data and model portal

{tile content}

WP leader: IIASA

Main objective: WP4 develops the ACT4CAP27 Portal to ensure effective exploration and dissemination of the project results to the target stakeholders within and outside the consortium.

Specific objectives:

O4.1 Develop a food system database with relevant economic, socio-economic and environmental indicators that supports the developments in WP2 and WP3.

O4.2 Designing and building the computational framework for interfacing the database with the novel modules.

O4.3 Designing and implementing the Scenario Explorer, an interactive and user-friendly tool for exploration and visualization of data and scenario results.

WP5 Modelling infrastructure and capacity building

{tile content}

WP leader: UPM

Main objective: to increase transparency and coherence in model use to build trust and bring model-based evidence

closer to policymaking.

Specific objectives:

O5.1 To ensure that the new analytical capacities and tools to support future evidence-based policies are made available and accessible to modelers, policymakers, and other end users.

O5.2 To ensure uptake of new modules in core models and build bridges between models

O5.3 To provide updated documentation for the assessment models.

O5.4 To advance the capacity of developing assessment models and using models and model results.

WP6 Assessments of EU agri-food policies post 2027

{tile content}

WP leader: Thuenen

Main objective: This WP aims to develop a comprehensive, effective, interrelated, integrated quantitative policy assessment for the CAP after 2027 and the future EU legal framework for sustainable food systems, using a two-step approach. A fast track will address important and timely issues using existing models, while the final track will incorporate modules developed in WP2 and WP3 and other improvements and expand models under the iMAP platform. The approach allows for structured repetition, addresses inconsistencies, and responds to new policy realities and data sources.

Specific objectives:

O6.1 Develop short term and long-term baselines to analyse policy assessment for the CAP after 2027 on FS indicators;

O6.2 Use a two-step approach: Fast track to address timely issues using existing models and a final track with enhanced toolbox including model improvements and expand collaboration under iMAP;

O6.3 Respond to new policy realities and document and compare progress in model development.

WP7 Stakeholder engagement and dissemination

{tile content}

WP leader: ECORYS

Main objective: Stakeholder engagement, project external communication, D&E activities.

Specific objectives:

O.7.1. To maintain a continuous dialogue with the EC and stakeholders and other key actors

O.7.2. To maximize the visibility of the project amongst target groups, and ensure project results reach end-users in effective ways

O.7.3. To maximise exploitation of project results and coordinate preparations for post-project exploitation

WP8 Management and Coordination

{tile content}

WP leader: WR

Main objective: To deliver a well-managed project to the Commission and all project stakeholders through:

Specific objectives:

O8.1 To ensure project research and innovation activities are managed and coordinated effectively.

O8.2 To ensure effective and efficient financial and administrative management of the project

O8.3 To ensure FAIR data management and high quality of the deliverables.

O8.4 To ensure synergies and linkages with other relevant projects.

WP9 Ethics requirements

{tile content}

WP leader: WR

Main objective: to ensure compliance with the required 'ethics requirements'.

Submenu 3: HOME > ABOUT > Partners

PARTNERS

The consortium of ACT4CAP27 consists of 13 partners from 10 countries in Europe (the Netherlands, Austria, Belgium, Germany, Italy, Hungary, Spain, Sweden, Ukraine, the United Kingdom), and the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission. The partners bring in expertise from modelling across different ecoclimatic conditions and socio-economic realities within Europe. It includes partners from the private and public sector representing: (a) Academia and higher education (LSHTM, PNU, SLU, UPM, UNIROMA3, WU); (b) SMEs dealing with research consultancy, data collection, and model development (EuroCARE), SMEs with a strong track record in the field of communication, stakeholder engagement and exploitation (POS, ECORYS); (c) Public government bodies and international research institutes dealing with agricultural and environmental research, data collection and, building agricultural models at different scales (WR, Thünen, IIASA).

For further information on each partner team please click on the following tiles:

[STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH \(WR\) More details](#)

[THÜNEN INSTITUTE \(Thunen\) More details](#)

[EUROPEAN CENTRE FOR AGRICULTURAL, REGIONAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY RESEARCH \(EUROCARE\) More details](#)

[INTERNATIONALES INSTITUT FUER ANGEWANDTE SYSTEMANALYSE \(IIASA\) More details](#)

[SVERIGES LANTBRUKSUNIVERSITET \(SLU\) More details](#)

[UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID \(UPM\) More details](#)

[WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY \(WU\) More details](#)

[POLISSIA NATIONAL UNIVERSITY \(PNU\) More details](#)

[UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI ROMA TRE \(UNIROMA3\) More details](#)

[ECORYS BRUSSELS NV \(ECORYS\) More details](#)

[POSSESSIO KFT \(POS\) More details](#)

[LONDON SCHOOL OF HYGIENE AND TROPICAL MEDICINE ROYAL CHARTER \(LSHTM\) More details](#)

[JOINT RESEARCH CENTRE- EUROPEAN COMMISSION \(JRC\) More details](#)

{Partners are to provide further information about their teams.}

The “News” page

1st news item:

ACT4CAP27 Kick-off in The Hague

<kick-off meeting group photo goes here>

13 partners from 10 European countries came together in the Hague on 18 March 2024 to mark the start of the 5-year research project “ACT4CAP27: Advancing Capacity and analytical tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027”.

The ACT4CAP27 project is funded through the European Commission’s Horizon Europe research programme. The kick-off was hosted by the Project Coordinator, Stichting Wageningen Research.

Attendees included representatives of all ACT4CAP27 partners, project- and scientific officers to the project at the European Commission and representatives of topic related fellow projects: BrightSpace and LAMASUS.

The ACT4CAP27 partners are:

- STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH (WR)
- THÜNEN INSTITUTE (Thunen)
- EUROPEAN CENTRE FOR AGRICULTURAL, REGIONAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY RESEARCH (EUROCARE)
- INTERNATIONALES INSTITUT FUER ANGEWANDTE SYSTEMANALYSE (IIASA)
- SVERIGES LANTBRUKSUNIVERSITET (SLU)
- UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID (UPM)
- WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY (WU)
- POLISSIA NATIONAL UNIVERSITY (PNU)
- UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI ROMA TRE (UNIROMA3)
- ECORYS BRUSSELS NV (ECORYS)
- POSSESSIO KFT (POS)
- LONDON SCHOOL OF HYGIENE AND TROPICAL MEDICINE ROYAL CHARTER (LSHTM)
- JOINT RESEARCH CENTRE- EUROPEAN COMMISSION (JRC)

Through active engagement of key stakeholders ACT4CAP27 aims to enhance analytical capabilities, tools, and collaborative technical infrastructure within the policy modelling community. This effort is directed towards providing continuous support for ex-ante analyses of EU agri-food policies post 2027 aligning with the objectives of the European Green Deal.

The fruitful discussions at the kick-off meeting benefitted from the multidisciplinary nature of the ACT4CAP27 team. Partners took this opportunity to share their experience and knowledge of the different themes to be tackled by the project. Decisions were made by the group regarding the various phases of the project. The kick off meeting successfully provided all partners with general guidance for undertaking the project, with a particular focus on the first part of the research.

The “Events” page

The events page feature upcoming and past events relevant for the project.

The “Resources” page

HOME > RESOURCES

{the following main categories as clickable tiles listed in one page}

Public deliverables

{Tile content: public deliverable titles with download link will be listed here}

Open-access scientific materials

{Tile content: links to open-access scientific materials will be listed here}

Policy briefs

{Tile content: policy briefings titles with download link will be listed here}

ACT4CAP27 in public repositories

{Tile content: links to public repositories e.g. OpenAIRE page, Zenodo Community will be listed here}

- ACT4CAP27 OpenAIRE page {link: <http://tinyurl.com/ACT4CAP27OpenAIRE>}
- ACT4CAP27 Zenodo Community {link: <https://zenodo.org/communities/act4cap27-eu-project>}

Final conference presentations and videos

{Tile content: final conference presentation titles with download link and link to videos will be listed here}

Presentations and posters

{Tile content: presentation titles and posters with download link will be listed here}

Other publications

{Tile content: Other publications, including promo material such as the on-line project flyer will be listed here}

Newsletters

{Tile content: links to electronic newsletters will be listed here}

Videos

{Tile content: links to video and podcast repositories will be listed here}

Media coverage

{Tile content: links to media coverage will be listed here}

Useful links

{Tile content: useful links will be listed here}

Modelling links

AGMEMOD: AGricultural MEmber State MODelling

CAPRI: Common Agricultural Policy Regionalised Impact Modelling System

EU Agri-Food Data Portal

EU Competence Centre On Modelling

EU JRC MIDAS: Modelling Inventory And Knowledge Management System

GLOBIOM: Global Biosphere Management Model

IFM-CAP: Individual Farm Model For Common Agricultural Policy Analysis

IAMC: Integrated Assessment Modelling Consortium

MAGNET: Modular Applied GeNeral Equilibrium Tool

Projects

BrightSpace HE GA Nr. 10106007: Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

LAMASUS HE: Land Management For Sustainability

Funding organization

Horizon Europe: Research And Innovation Funding Programme

More useful links will be added as the project progresses.

The website footer

KEEP IN TOUCH

PROJECT COORDINATOR

Siemen van Berkum, Project Coordinator (WR)

Hans van Meijl, Scientific Coordinator (WR)

act4cap27(at)wur.nl

Social network links and Newsletter subscription

Social network links

{X link} <https://twitter.com/ACT4CAP27>

{YouTube link} <https://www.youtube.com/@ACT4CAP27-horizon-eu-project>

{LinkedIn link} <https://www.linkedin.com/company/act4cap27-eu-project/>

{Zenodo link} <https://zenodo.org/communities/act4cap27-eu-project>

{OpenAIRE link} <http://tinyurl.com/ACT4CAP27OpenAIRE>

SUBSCRIBE TO OUR NEWSLETTERS

{field for first name input} {field for last name input}

{field for email address input}

{checkbox} I have read and agree to the privacy policy.

{button} Subscribe

© ACT4CAP27 2024 | Privacy & Cookie Policy {<https://ACT4CAP27-project.eu/privacy-policy>}

| Imprint {<https://ACT4CAP27-project.eu/imprint/>}

Bottom section: funding acknowledgment

For the acknowledgement text font type face it is compulsory to use Arial.

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The “Privacy and Cookie Policy” page

{Content text as follows:}

WEBSITE PRIVACY AND COOKIE POLICY

Contents

1. Introduction
2. The personal data that we collect
3. Purposes of processing and legal bases
4. Providing your personal data to others
5. International transfers of your personal data
6. Retaining and deleting personal data
7. Your rights
8. About cookies
9. Cookies that we use
10. Cookies used by our service providers
11. How to control or delete cookies
12. Integration of Services and Content by Third Parties

13. Links to other websites
14. Amendments
15. Data protection officer

1. Introduction

This website is dedicated to the dissemination of the ACT4CAP27 project funded by the European Union under Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No 101134874 and receives funding from UKRI under Project Code: 101134874.

The ACT4CAP27 consortium is committed to the protection of your personal data and respects your privacy on its website on the www.act4cap27.eu domain). Our website complies with the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679.

This Privacy and Cookie Policy applies to all ACT4CAP27 website users and outlines how our website collects, uses, discloses, and manages the personal information of individuals. This serves as a transparency mechanism, informing users about the ways in which their personal data is handled and protected by our project, and what choices you have as a visitor to this website.

By visiting our site, you are accepting the practices described in our Privacy and Cookie Policy. If you do not agree to the terms of this Privacy and Cookie Policy, please do not use the site.

As a data subject, you must be aware that some of your personal data is collected and maintained by our website for a certain period and for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes. Personal data shall be treated fairly and in a transparent manner in accordance with the applicable legal framework and in such a way as to guarantee the key data protection principles, namely:

- Lawfulness, fairness and transparency
- Processing within the legitimate purpose limits
- Data minimization
- Accuracy
- Storage Limitation
- Integrity and confidentiality (security)
- Accountability

2. The personal data that we collect

There are several ways in which we can collect information about you:

- We collect your first name, last name and e-mail address when you subscribe to our newsletter.
- We may also collect your personal data (your name, your organization name, country, your contact details and the message itself) if you contact us via the contact form in our website, via social media, e-mail, phone, or any other digital communication channel. We will use this data only to reply to your initial message, unless you agree to receive further information related to the ACT4CAP27 Project.

- We collect certain information about you when you use this webpage via cookies. Further details on this are provided in our Cookie Policy in Sections 8 to 11.

The ACT4CAP27 website does not collect, process or gain access in any way to specific categories of personal data, as set forth in the provisions of the legislation in force (in particular data relating to racial or ethnic origin, religion, health data, etc.).

3. Purposes of processing and legal bases

We process your personal data for the following purposes:

- If you subscribed to the newsletter: to regularly send you the INCISIVE newsletter, including invitations to events and webinars about the project. You may also receive email from us with questions and information about your subscription to our newsletter. You always have the opportunity to unsubscribe from our newsletter by clicking on the link provided in the newsletter or by contacting us at [act4cap27\(at\)wur.nl](mailto:act4cap27@wur.nl).
- When you contact us through the contact form or via phone, e-mail or other digital communication channel: to answer the questions received via the contact form.
- Keep the website secure and prevent fraud.
- Improve the website content and experience by analysing the user's performance.
- Verify compliance with the terms and conditions governing the use of the Website.

The legal bases for collecting and using your data:

- If you subscribe to our newsletter, you are providing your consent which is the legal basis on which we process your personal data. Your consent is voluntary but necessary to receive the newsletter. You may withdraw your consent at any time by clicking on the link provided in the newsletter or by contacting us at [act4cap27\(at\)wur.nl](mailto:act4cap27@wur.nl).
- If you contact us via our contract form or via phone, e-mail or other digital communication channel and for web analytics purposes we rely on our legitimate interest to be able to respond to your message, request or a question or improve the performance of our website.

The purposes for which we use data obtained by our cookies are described in our Cookie Policy in Sections 8 to 11.

We may also process your personal data to comply with legal obligations or to comply, insofar we are legally allowed, with any reasonable request from competent law enforcement agents or representatives, judicial authorities, governmental agencies or bodies, including competent data protection authorities.

4. Providing your personal data to others

We will only share your personal data when necessary. Where possible, data will be anonymized and/or aggregated.

The information collected from the website may, when necessary, be shared with:

- the ACT4CAP27 consortium partners (i.e. if you ask a question relating to the role of a particular partner). The list of the partners is available here [<https://ACT4CAP27-project.eu/about/partners/>];

- potentially also with the European Commission when reporting ACT4CAP27 results, or governmental or judicial authorities insofar we are required by law to send them your personal data (e.g. police or law enforcement).

We will not share your personal data with anyone but our suppliers who help us process your personal data.

Our use of analytical and statistical cookies may imply that the third-party provider of those cookies, namely Google, may obtain certain information about you, including about your surfing behaviour. You may find more information on Google's processing activities here: <https://support.google.com/analytics/answer/6004245?hl=en>.

Anyone who has access to your personal data will always be bound by strict legal or contractual obligations to keep your personal data safe and confidential. ACT4CAP27 will not, without your express consent, supply your personal data to any third party for marketing purposes, whether directly or indirectly.

Anonymised and aggregated statistics about the use of the website, may be shared within the ACT4CAP27 consortium and with the European Commission, but this will not contain any information that can be traced back to you as a user.

5. International transfers of your personal data

We do not intend to send your personal data outside of EEA. However, we have consortium partners based in the UK. We may need to share your data with them if – for example – your request pertains to their organizations. In case any transfer of personal data outside the European Economic Area (the European Economic Area consists of the EU, Liechtenstein, Norway and Iceland) would occur, we assure you that we will only do so in accordance with either Art. 45 GDPR (on the basis of an adequacy decision) or Art 46 GDPR (appropriate safeguards in place).

6. Retaining and deleting personal data

We process and store personal data as long as it necessary for the fulfilment of our contractual obligations under the Grant Agreement of the project. When this data is no longer necessary for the above purposes, it will be regularly deleted.

All personal data we collect to send you our newsletter we will keep for as long as you remain subscribed to our mailing list.

Regarding data collected through cookies your personal data are only processed at the first moment of collection. Afterwards we immediately use the anonymization features of Google Analytics to ensure that any information collected via cookies is anonymized.

We may keep reports and aggregated statistical data for up to 5 years after the project's duration.

7. Your rights

You enjoy a number of rights which you can exercise in the manner described below. You have the right:

- To ask us whether we process personal data on you, and if so, to obtain access to your personal data processed by us. You can also obtain a copy of your data.

- To correct/ update your personal data. If possible, please specify the context in which we use your personal data (e.g. to send you newsletters or to respond to a request), so that we may assess your request swiftly and accurately.
- To request deletion of your data, where applicable. For example, this right could be exercised in cases where the personal data is no longer necessary, the personal data processing is unlawful, or you withdraw your consent.
- To request restriction of the processing of your personal data, where applicable. This could for example be a temporary measure in the case where you contest the accuracy of the personal data of you object to the processing, pending our review of your request.
- To receive the personal data, which you have provided on the website, in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format and to transmit those data to another controller without hindrance from the us (data portability). However, this right only applies to personal data you have provided to us and if they were provided on the basis of your consent or because they were necessary for the execution or the performance of an agreement with you>
- To object to processing of your data. You can exercise this right when we process your personal data on the basis of our legitimate interests, i.e. you have not given us your consent and we do not need them for the execution or performance of an agreement nor to comply with legal obligations. When our interest relates to direct marketing, we will grant you your request immediately. For other interests, e.g. our security interests, we will ask you to describe your specific circumstances giving rise to request. We then need to balance our interests against your circumstances. If this balancing exercise results in your circumstances outweighing our interests, we will cease processing your personal data.
- To withdraw your consent for the processing of personal data when we have collected your personal data on the basis of your consent. The withdrawal of consent does not affect the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal.

You can exercise these rights by sending an email to [act4cap27\(at\)wur.nl](mailto:act4cap27@wur.nl) When doing so, please make sure to provide any information needed to confirm your identify.

Organisations have an obligation to respond to any request to consult, modify or delete your personal data within 30 days. However, this period may be renewed if the request concerns a large amount of data. In any case, you will be informed as soon as possible of the time required for processing the request.

In case you remain unsatisfied with our response you have the right to contact the competent supervisory authority of the Member State. In the Netherlands, the supervisory authority is the Dutch Data Protection Agency: <https://autoriteitpersoonsgegevens.nl/en> The list of the European data protection authorities is available on the website of European Data Protection Board (https://edpb.europa.eu/about-edpb/board/members_en).

8. About cookies

During users' navigation on this website, we may collect identification data of users, by using cookies.

Cookies are short software code texts, which are sent from our website hosting server and are stored at your terminal ("browser"). Their basic function is to communicate to us data from your browser.

First party cookies are cookies set by the website you are visiting. Only that website can read them. In addition, a website might potentially use external services, which also set their own cookies, known as third-party cookies.

Persistent cookies are cookies saved on your computer and that are not deleted automatically when you quit your browser, unlike a session cookie, which is deleted when you quit your browser.

Every time you visit the ACT4CAP27 website, you will be prompted to accept or refuse cookies.

The purpose is to enable the site to remember your preferences (such as user name, language, etc.) for a certain period of time.

That way, you do not have to re-enter them when browsing around the site during the same visit.

Cookies can also be used to establish anonymised statistics about the browsing experience on our sites.

Cookies do not have access to data on your hard disk or cookies created by other sites and do not damage your system.

You may control and/or delete all cookies from your computer and, in most browsers, select settings that do not allow installation of cookies. However, in that case, you may have to adjust certain preferences every time you visit a website.

Users may make use of the website without problems even without use of cookies, but, potentially, to the detriment of its user-friendliness and of the functioning of certain of its services. Any personal data collected via cookies that can be correlated to a specific visitor/user shall be processed exclusively for the purposes cited above.

For more information about cookies, please visit <http://www.allaboutcookies.org/>

9. Cookies that we use

The types of cookies used by us and our partners in connection with the ACT4CAP27 website can be classified into one of four categories, namely ‘functionality cookies’ necessary for essential Website purposes, , performance and analytics cookies’, ‘tracking cookies’, and ‘social media cookies’. We have set out some further information about each category, and the purposes of the cookies we and third-parties set as follows.

Functionality Cookies

Functionality cookies record information about choices you have made and allow us to tailor the website to you. These cookies mean that when you continue to use or come back to the Platform, we can provide you with our services as you have asked for them to be provided. For example, these cookies allow us to:

- Save your location preference if you have set your location on your homepage, if applicable.
- Remember settings you have applied, such as layout, text size, preferences, and colours;
- Show you when you are logged in; and
- Store accessibility options. Please see the instructions set out in ‘How to control or delete cookies’ below.

Performance and Analytics Cookies

We use Google Analytics as web analytics tool that helps us understand how users engage with our website. Like many services, these web analytics services use first party cookies to track user interactions as in our case, where they are used to collect information about how users use our site and how they use it. This information is used to compile reports and create services to help us improve our website and the services associated with it.

The reports disclose website trends without identifying individual visitors. Some services will allow you to opt out of tracking with their services directly. For instance, while you cannot opt out of use of cookies with our site, you can opt out of Google Analytics without affecting how you visit our site. For more information on opting out of being tracked by Google Analytics across all websites you use, visit this Google page. <https://support.google.com/analytics/answer/6004245?hl=en>

Social Media Cookies

On some pages of our website, third parties that provide applications through our website may set their own cookies in order to track the success of their applications or customise applications for you. For example, when you share a content using a social media sharing button on our Platform (e.g., Facebook, Twitter, or Google Plus), the social network that has created the button will record that you have done this. Because of how cookies work, we cannot access these cookies, nor can the third parties access the data in cookies used by us. Some pages of our website may also contain embedded content, such as video content from YouTube, and these third-party sites may set their own cookies. Please see the instructions set out in ‘How to control or delete cookies’ below.

The cookies we use collect the following data:

- Time of visit, pages visited, and time spent on each page of the webpages
- Referring site details (such as the URI a user came through to arrive at this site)
- Type of web browser
- Type of operating system (OS)
- Flash version, JavaScript support, screen resolution, and screen color processing ability
- Network location and IP address.

10. Cookies used by our service providers

- [YouTube](#)
- [Twitter](#)
- [Vimeo](#)
- [Microsoft](#)
- [Google](#)
- [LinkedIn](#)
- [SoundCloud](#)

These third-party services are outside of the control of the ACT4CAP27 consortium. Providers may, at any time, change their terms of service, purpose and use of cookies, etc.

11. How to Control or Delete Cookies

You have the right to accept or stop cookies from being stored on your device at any time by modifying the settings in your web browser to reflect your cookie preferences.

Please be aware that you may not be able to use all the interactive features of our services, the website and its content once cookies are disabled.

Most browsers offer instructions on how to change your cookie settings. These settings will typically be found in the options or preferences menu of your browser. In order to understand these settings, the following links may be helpful, otherwise you should use the ‘Help’ option in your browser for more details.

- [Cookie settings in Microsoft Edge](#)
- [Cookie settings in Firefox](#)
- [Cookie settings in Chrome](#)
- Cookie settings in [Safari web](#) and [iOS](#).

12. Integration of Services and Content by Third Parties

It may happen that content or third-party services such as city maps or fonts from other websites are integrated into our Online Services. Integration of third-party content always requires that they know the User’s IP address, since they will not be able to send the content to the User’s browser without the IP address . The IP address is therefore required in order to display this content. In addition, providers of third-party content may set their own cookies and process the Users’ data for their own purposes. User profiles may be created from the processed data. We will use this kind of content as sparingly as possible to prevent unwanted transfer of data and will select reliable Third-Party Providers in terms of data security.

The following list provides an overview of Third-Party Providers and their contents as well as links to their privacy policies, which contain further information on the processing of data and, as in some cases already mentioned here, the possibility to object (called “opt-out”):

– External fonts from Google, Inc. <https://www.google.com/fonts> (“Google Fonts”). The integration of Google Fonts is done by a server call on Google (usually in the US). Privacy: <https://policies.google.com/privacy?hl=en>, Opt-Out: <https://www.google.com/settings/ads/>.

– Maps from the “Google Maps” service of the Third-Party Provider Google Inc., 1600 Amphitheatre Parkway, Mountain View, CA 94043, USA. Privacy: <https://policies.google.com/privacy?hl=en>, Opt-Out: <https://www.google.com/settings/ads/>.

— Videos from the “YouTube” platform of the Third-Party Provider Google Inc., 1600 Amphitheatre Parkway, Mountain View, CA 94043, USA. Privacy: <https://policies.google.com/privacy?hl=en>, Opt-Out: <https://www.google.com/settings/ads/>.

Google Analytics

We use Google Analytics, a web analytics service provided by Google Inc. (“Google”). Google uses cookies. The information generated by the cookie about the use of the website by the User is usually transferred to a Google server in the United States of America and stored there.

Google will use this information on our behalf to evaluate the use of our website by Users, to compile reports on the activities on this website, and to provide us with other services related to the use of this website and the internet. The processed data may be used to create pseudonymized user profiles.

We only use Google Analytics with IP anonymization enabled. This means that the IP address of the User is shortened by Google within EU Member States or other contracting states of the Agreement on the European Economic Area. Only in exceptional cases will the full IP address be transmitted to a Google server in the United States and shortened there.

The IP address transmitted by the User's browser is not merged with other Google data. Users can prevent the storage of cookies by adjusting their browser software accordingly; Users can also prevent the collection of data which is generated by the cookie and transmitted to Google for processing in connection with their use of the Online Services by downloading and installing the browser plugin which is available at: <http://tools.google.com/dlpage/gaoptout>.

For more information on the use of Google data for advertising purposes, setting options and opt-out options, please visit Google's websites: <https://www.google.com/intl/en/policies/privacy/partners> (How Google uses information from sites or apps that use our services), <https://policies.google.com/technologies/ads?hl=en> (How Google uses cookies in advertising), <http://www.google.de/settings/ads> (Control the information Google uses to show you ads) and <https://adssettings.google.com/authenticated?hl=en> (Ad personalization).

Social Media Tools

Our website uses Social Plugins (Plugins) of different social networks like Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube, which are marked by their logos. When you open a site with these plugins, browser data is transferred to the owners of those social networks. Thus, they are informed that you have opened the respective site. If you are logged in to one or several of these social networks, this data can be linked to your account. Your IP address may be logged without you being a member of a social network or logging into a network.

In that case, please note that the processing of data takes place outside of the European Union. We have no influence on and take no responsibility for the volume of data that is transferred through social plugins.

For more information, please look up the data security policies of the respective network:

twitter.com/privacy

<https://www.linkedin.com/legal/privacy-policy>

https://www.youtube.com/static?template=privacy_guidelines

Newsletter Services

We use MailerLite to manage our email marketing subscriber list and to send emails to our subscribers. MailerLite is a third-party provider, which may process your data (when you subscribe) using industry-standard technologies to help us monitor and improve our newsletter. MailerLite's privacy policy is available at <https://www.mailerlite.com/legal/privacy-policy>

You can always unsubscribe from our newsletter by clicking on the unsubscribe link provided at the end of each newsletter. You may also contact us using the information below to request a complete deletion of your data from our Newsletter Service.

13. Links to other websites

The website contains links to other websites. The ACT4CAP27 consortium are not responsible for data privacy policies and/or practices on other websites and have no influence as to whether the operators of other websites act in compliance with data protection provisions. The ACT4CAP27 Privacy and Cookie Policy is solely applicable to data collected by ACT4CAP27 project website itself.

14. Amendments

The terms and conditions of this Privacy and Cookie Policy can be adjusted without prior notice. Changes are effective as soon as they are published on the website. Your continued use of our site following the posting of changes to these terms will mean you accept those changes.

15. Data protection officer

The data protection laws require that we provide you with information on the processing of your personal data. Should you have further questions regarding the processing of your personal data, the ACT4CAP27 Data Protection Officer can be contacted via email at Act4cap27(at)wur.nl

The “Imprint” page

{Content text as follows:}

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The website may contain links to third party websites for the sole purpose of providing information to the user / visitor. The referral to links belonging to third-party websites does not constitute an endorsement of their views and actions or the acceptance of the content they express, publish or post. Third-parties -owners of the websites/responsible under the law- are solely responsible for the content of their websites or for any damage that may result from their use when the user / visitor of the Website gains access to them.

The Consortium makes all efforts to ensure the proper function of its network but does not guarantee that its server operations will be uninterrupted or error-free, free from viruses, malicious software or other similar elements.

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APPENDIX 1

Figure 1 ACT4CAP27 project colour scheme

Possessio

<https://act4cap27.eu>

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101134874>

<http://tinyurl.com/ACT4CAP27OpenAIRE>